

WAYS TO ENSURE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC STABILITY OF CHEMICAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: *This article describes the ways to ensure the financial and economic stability of enterprises in the chemical industry. The author proposes a strategy to ensure the economic stability of chemical enterprises of Uzbekistan, first of all, to ensure their economic security.*

Keywords: *financial and economic stability, chemical industry, economic security, chemical industry products, competitiveness.*

The current state of the global chemical industry shows that one of the main factors negatively affecting the development of the industry is the cost of geological exploration. "Worldwide, these costs have fallen by more than 60% and in 2014 amounted to \$ 153 billion. About \$ 58 billion in 2017. Up to USD. The sharp decline in investment has a direct impact on the volume of production at new deposits "[1]. According to chemical industry experts, demand for oil and gas is higher than the annual forecast, while oil and gas reserves are declining, while commodity reserves are declining. In this regard, the launch of new deposits through geological exploration in a number of countries, including the United States, China, the Russian Federation and Kazakhstan, is an important task.

Reduction of geological prospecting costs in the developed countries of the chemical industry with the widespread use of resource and energy saving technologies in this area; expansion of product range and cost reduction; Extensive research in the areas of creating an institutional, legal and investment environment for the formation of a modern national chemical industry, economic incentives for chemical enterprises, modernization of the chemical industry, the widespread introduction of market mechanisms in management, development of organizational and economic mechanisms to ensure economic stability of chemical enterprises is being carried out. Also, the study of scientific-methodological and practical aspects of ensuring the economic stability of enterprises of the chemical industry on the basis of modern approaches is one of the current scientific directions.

Extensive measures are being taken to increase the global competitiveness of the national economy of Uzbekistan, including the chemical industry. The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, in particular, "further transforming industry through a qualitatively new stage aimed at the rapid development of high-tech processing industries, primarily the production of high value-added finished products based on deep processing of local raw materials modernization and diversification "[2]. Therefore, it is important to comprehensively develop the internal

capacity of industrial enterprises to increase their economic stability, radically update their material and technical base and conduct research on the efficient use of available resources.

In our view, the concept of "financial and economic stability" starts from the point of view of industrial enterprises, as any scientific approach, always systematizing the concepts used by scientists and practitioners. Modern approaches to enterprise sustainability A. Vald, L. Valras, P. Samuelson, A.A. Bogdanov, V.S. Rappoportva is based on the scientific work of other scientists. In particular, A. Vald, L. Valras, P. Samuelson, Dj. R. Hicks and others first considered the concept of "sustainability" in terms of economic systems. The main results in the field of sustainability were obtained by them when studying the market equilibrium and the conditions for achieving them.

Based on the views of local and foreign scientists who have conducted research in this field and their definitions, the financial and economic stability of the chemical industry is a guarantee of profitability and sustainable development of the enterprise. and the ability to maintain a certain level of financial and economic parameters, which allows to restore the original equilibrium or to adopt a new one after the cessation of external and internal factors in the present and in the future.

Based on the analysis of existing methods and approaches in the world, taking into account the specifics of the chemical industry, it is proposed to improve the methodology for assessing the level of economic stability of chemical enterprises in accordance with financial, production, technological, marketing and organizational criteria. [3]

The assessment of the financial and economic stability of the chemical industry should be carried out using the average geometric indicators for each industry, taking into account the specific characteristics of each industry. This is because each network enterprise is affected by external and internal factors, which leads to uncertainties in the implementation of mathematical calculations. The assessment of the economic sustainability of the chemical industry should use as little expert assessment as possible, firstly, if there are uncertainties in the survey results, and secondly, the limited opportunities to find and select experienced experts. [4]

It should be noted that the effectiveness of a security policy is only at the desired level when it is the result of the joint efforts of employees of the organization who are able to understand all its aspects and managers who can influence its implementation. The organization can invest heavily in providing security against external threats, protecting trade secrets in information systems, but internal conflicts can arise due to internal reasons, such as incompetence of the company's management or lack of mutual understanding. [5]

The organizational and economic mechanism of ensuring the financial and economic risk of the chemical industry, proposed by the author, on the one hand, allows the introduction of a system of early detection of economic risks, on the other hand, allows to form rational management decisions handles can be improved based on development.

Figure 1. Organizational and economic mechanism of financial and economic security in enterprises

Source: Author's development.

Prospective medium and long-term development of the chemical industry in Uzbekistan is determined by the volume of investments in the modernization of the material and technical base of enterprises and the level of competitiveness of products in domestic and foreign markets. The investment activity of enterprises will be a key factor in shaping the demand for chemical products. The logical result of technological innovations in the chemical industry should be to increase the competitiveness of the industry in the domestic and foreign markets.

It is recommended to consider the main possible scenarios for the development of the industry in the framework of a comprehensive state program on import substitution. Alternative scenarios are based on the forecast of the development of the market of chemical products by 2025 and depend on the level, forms and methods of state support for the industry.

During the study, a strategy was proposed to ensure the financial and economic sustainability of chemical enterprises in Uzbekistan, first of all, to ensure their economic security. The strategy includes the development of measures to combat internal and external risks, as well as the modernization of existing oil and gas refineries and the construction of new production facilities, the formation of deep processing systems at enterprises, the widespread use of modern innovative technologies, transport and logistics system and increase oil and gas production through accelerated development of raw material bases.

In ensuring the financial and economic stability of the enterprises of the chemical industry of Uzbekistan, the following measures should be taken: acceleration of the process of modernization and technical and technological armament of enterprises; write-off and sale of unused and non-specialized assets on the balance sheet of enterprises; sale of the state share in the charter capital of enterprises to investors; drastic reduction of costs of mining, processing and sales through the introduction of modern management systems and tools in enterprises; the use and control of modern standards of environmental safety in the extraction and processing of hydrocarbons.

REFERENCES:

1. https://www.strategyand.pwc.com/media/file/Oil-Gas-Trends-2018-19_RU.pdf

2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017. On the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan // Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2017. - № 6 (766). - 32-33-b.

3. Link, David F., et al. "Management techniques for non-traditional network and information system topologies". U.S. Patent No. 9,537,731. 3 Jan. 2017.

4. Makarova E.V. The specificity of the stability of the economic system of the region. // Proceedings of the III International Scientific and Practical Conference "Problems of Socio-Economic Sustainability of the Region". - Penza: RIO PGSHA, 2006.

5. Maxmudov N.M. Strengthening macroeconomic stability is an important condition for sustainable economic growth // Economics and Education. № 2. 2017. - pp. 7-11.